

Using Bloom’s Taxonomy in Rubrics for Assessing Writing and Speaking Skills

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Abstract: This research uses Bloom’s taxonomy in English-language writing and speaking skills assessment rubrics. A descriptive qualitative research method was adopted, and data were collected through observations, interviews, and English major students’ course grades. Five lecturers and 25 students participated in the research, and the findings revealed that applying Bloom’s taxonomy in an assessment rubric focuses on cognitive assessment at the two lowest levels, namely knowledge and understanding. We also identified five benefits of applying Bloom’s taxonomy, mainly motivating students and improving learning performance based on the criteria. Therefore, the assessments helped the lecturers and students achieve their teaching and learning goals. The findings presented here have implications for developing learning curricula, improving basic competencies, creating indicators for achieving semester learning plans, and achieving educational goals at local and international levels.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Bloom
Puanlama anahtarı
Değerlendirme
Yazma
Konuşma

Yazma ve Konuşma Becerilerinin Değerlendirilmesinde Bloom’un Sınıflandırmasının Kullanımı

Özet: Bu araştırmada İngilizce yazma ve konuşma becerilerinin değerlendirilmesinde Bloom’un sınıflandırmasının kullanılması incelenmektedir. Araştırmada betimleyici nitel bir araştırma yöntemi kullanılmış ve veriler de gözlemler, görüşmeler ve İngilizce öğrenim gören öğrencilerin aldıkları ders başarı notlarından oluşmaktadır. Araştırmaya beş öğretim görevlisi ve 25 öğrenci katılmıştır. Bulgular, Bloom’un sınıflandırmasının bir değerlendirme ölçütü olarak kullanıldığında en düşük iki düzeyde, yani bilgi ve anlamada kendini göstermiştir. Bloom’un sınıflandırmasının kullanımında özellikle beş belirgin yarar ön plana çıkmıştır ki bunlar öğrencileri motive etmek ve kriterlere göre öğrenme performansını iyileştirmeye işaret eder. Teknolojiyi uygulamadaki çeşitli engeller üniversiteden ciddi derece bir işlem gerektirmektedir. Çalışmanın doğruları arasında öğretim programlarının geliştirilmesi, temel yeterliliklerin iyileştirilmesi, dönemlik öğretim planlarının gerçekleştirilmesi ve yerel ve uluslararası düzeyde eğitim hedeflerine ulaşılması bulunmaktadır.

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1. Introduction

Mastering English is also necessary to access information sources worldwide to help various aspects of life and improve our overall competence. By becoming proficient in English, students can develop a broader understanding of cultural diversity and improve their general learning abilities (Benmokhtari, 2021). The literature posits that learning English has a positive impact on personality development, especially in terms of aspects like self-confidence, problem-solving skills, professionalism, and the ability to adapt to people from various backgrounds (Galloway & Ruegg, 2020; Sah, 2022). Many universities in Indonesia provide opportunities for students to major in English. Moreover, the job prospects for foreign-language graduates are broad, and they can support socioeconomic progress and make a real positive impact, so English is quite a popular subject among high school graduates (Alrajafi, 2021; Choi, 2024).

Previous research (Dunifa, 2023) on English language learners' speaking abilities revealed that these students' speaking skills

are weak and insufficient with the following characteristics: (1) they speak slowly and unevenly; (2) they frequently make mistakes in their pronunciation, which makes understanding them challenging; (3) they consistently make mistakes in their grammar, demonstrating a limited command of the major patterns and impeding communication; (4) their word choices are inaccurate, and their vocabulary limitations prevent them from discussing several common professional and social topics; and (5) they can only understand easy and sluggish conversation. (p. 46)

In line with this, recent studies also indicated that writing in English at the tertiary level is one of the most challenging skills (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023; Hazaea, 2023; Saricaoglu & Atak, 2022; Zorba, 2023). Considering all these, the research, therefore, sets out to determine the usefulness of Bloom's taxonomy in the assessment rubric for students majoring in English at UIN RM Said. To achieve this goal, we investigated the steps by which Bloom's taxonomy was applied. The findings of this study will contribute to our knowledge about improving speaking and writing ability in a foreign language.

1.1. Bloom's Taxonomy in Assessment

Assessment is an important element of the student learning process, and it is measured through various procedures. Such evaluation practices are needed to indicate if there has been a significant improvement for students. Learning assessment has two goals, namely, to obtain a summative evaluation of students' progress and provide instructional feedback to help students further this progress.

Lukita *et al.* (2020) explained that the Indonesian guide to preparing higher education curricula mentions five assessment principles, namely (1) educational assessment motivates students to improve their planning and learning methods and achieve graduate learning outcomes; (2) authentic assessment is oriented toward a continuous learning process with learning outcomes that reflect students' abilities; (3) objective assessment is based on standards that are agreed between the teacher and students and free from any subjective influences; (4) accountable assessment is carried out through clear procedures and criteria that the students understand; and (5) transparent assessment is where all stakeholders can access procedures and assessment results.

In the framework of Bloom's taxonomy, educational assessment is divided into three aspects of intellectual ability. First, *cognitive ability* refers to aspects such as knowledge and thinking

skills. *Affective ability*, in contrast, relates to emotions, such as feelings, interests, and motivation. Finally, *psychomotor ability* emphasizes the function of physical or motor skills. In practice, the learning process can start at any level of Bloom's taxonomy depending on the teacher's preference, and the steps within it are very suitable for integrated learning (Acharya & Nepal, 2024).

The literature has explained the significance of applying Bloom's taxonomy to bridge educational gaps in higher education. In addition, Bloom's taxonomy also relates to assessment and learning, such as for the teacher engaging in the teaching and learning process, compiling the curriculum, choosing the right key verbs, and so on. This plays an important role in explaining the learning objectives and basic competencies, so material concepts can be conveyed effectively. For example, verbs act a reference for teachers in determining the depth of the material to be delivered (Aheisibwe et al., 2021). Preparing a learning plan comprises five stages: (1) determining the learning objectives set by the teacher; (2) determining the competencies to be achieved; (3) determining any friendly intellectual abilities as learning competencies; (4) using appropriate key verbs to explain the depth of material; and finally (5) determining appropriate learning media (Akinboboye & Ayanwale, 2021). Bloom's taxonomy has also been found to increase student competency in various subjects, such as business, English, and management (Acharya & Nepal, 2024; Ching & Da Silva, 2017).

Benjamin Bloom created Bloom's taxonomy (see Fig. 1) as a hierarchical classification for different levels of thinking (Bloom & Krathwohl, 1956). It can, therefore, be used to categorize the levels of reasoning skills that students use for active learning. Based on Bloom's taxonomy, six levels can be applied to learning: knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Bloom's taxonomy

1.2. Rubrics in Assessing Writing and Speaking

A rubric is a tool or instrument to help teachers establish assignment assessment criteria. This is not only useful for teachers but also for students. A rubric has four features: First, a task description details the task students are expected to perform. Second, a scale and score

describe the level of mastery, such as whether it meets, exceeds, or fails to meet expectations. Third, it identifies the components or dimensions students must focus on when completing assignments. Fourth, it describes the performance quality of these components or dimensions at each level of mastery (Reddy & Andrade, 2010). As in many other forms of writing, rubrics are used to evaluate writing while providing learners with standardized, accurate, and applicable feedback (Arikan, 2006, p. 8).

Some studies criticize using rubrics as only useful for high-stakes testing and other periodic assessment situations. Moreover, some symbols used in a rubric may need to represent the criteria accurately. According to Andrade *et al.* (2019), however, rubrics can improve students' academic performance and help them to produce better-quality work, so the value obtained through the learning process will be greater. Nevertheless, not all students enjoy reading rubrics thoroughly, and language assessment in a written form must be authentic. In turn, for a measure to be authentic, students must believe that it relates to their lives or goals in a topic. The resulting assessment can also be formative and collaborative, with a rubric score being developed by students based on mastery and contextual realism.

The materials that can be used for assessing writing skills include (1) an essay where the author's ideas on a topic are stated throughout; (2) an essay in the form of a letter, report, instructions, or announcement; (3) grammar in the form of linguistic devices that are adapted to applicable rules while meeting the requirements of written language; (4) refined spelling that regulates the mechanism for transferring spoken language into written language; and (5) the neatness of students' writing (Berge *et al.*, 2016). Speaking skill, meanwhile, comprises three dimensions, including (1) the use of spoken language as a medium for conversation with vocabulary, language structure, pronunciation and intonation, language variety and politeness, and sequence; (2) the use of conversational content depending on the topic of discussion; (3) a mastery of speaking techniques and performances that can be adapted to the situation and nature of the conversation, which in this situation would be presenting paper assignments and engaging in class discussions.

Several systematic literature reviews have investigated the use of rubrics for assessing writing and speaking for learning purposes. For example, the study of Shabani and Panahi (2020) found that rubrics are allegedly very useful as a practical tool for assessing the quality of writing assignments, with their results showing higher scores for them. Other studies have looked at the use of rubrics in the assessment of research reports (Bukhari, *et al.*, 2021) and in teacher education (Arikan, 2006).

1.3. Research Question

Based on the background of the study described above, this study tried to understand the benefits of using Bloom's taxonomy in assessing English major students' writing and speaking skills.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The research procedure for this study was based on a case study research design, with the research topic being learning assessment rubrics based on the cognitive levels of Bloom's taxonomy at an Islamic university in Indonesia. Specifically, UIN RM Said Surakarta is in Central Java Province. Using qualitative research methods, the author conducted semi-structured interviews about applying Bloom's taxonomy in the assessment rubric for writing

and speaking English. The study also employed in-depth observation, which can help understand the substance and provide a clearer picture of the specific issues studied scientifically. As is usual with qualitative characteristics, the author used appropriate procedures to obtain data, limited the research to the assumptions of a qualitative approach, and started with a single focus so that the readers could experience the sense of this research. The research period was one semester, ending when the teaching lecturer completed the assessment.

2.2. Participants

The participants for this research comprised five-course lecturers in the English department and 25 of their students for the 2023/2024 academic year. The criteria for participating lecturers included having a semester learning plan (RPS), having a rubric for assessing writing and speaking English for at least one semester, and applying Bloom's taxonomy in the classroom learning process. The inclusion criteria for students were that (1) they needed to have passed with good marks in the prerequisite courses; (2) they needed to have an average GPA above 3.00; and (3) they needed to be receiving an English writing and speaking rubric assessment from the teaching lecturer. Some prerequisite courses that students had to complete before participating included intensive listening, intensive speaking, intensive reading, intensive writing, English paragraph writing, academic writing, and intermediate English grammar.

2.3. Instrument

The research instruments were observations, interviews, and the student score data obtained by applying an assessment rubric based on Bloom's taxonomy. The research focused on providing concrete evidence of student progress because while students may say they are happy with an English course, they do not know whether they are learning to write and speak any better. For this reason, the instrument is structured based on three dimensions: (1) the thinking skills that students want to develop, (2) the formation of learning activities, and (3) simple tasks like writing scientific papers, memorizing words, and presenting paper assignments. The aspects that were assessed included the paper's content, the organization of ideas, and the language and mechanics of the paper. Other writing criteria included the clarity of the topic, systematic writing, cohesive and coherent paragraphs, and good spelling and grammar. The speaking criteria, meanwhile, included pronunciation, intonation, vocabulary, grammar, speaking fluency, and the understanding of topics.

2.4. Data Collection Methods

Three types of data collection were used by the author, namely observations, interviews, and documentation from primary and secondary data sources. Observations were systematically carried out by focusing on, and directly studying, participant behavior and the teaching and learning process. Face-to-face semi-structured interviews were conducted based on an interview guide with specific questions and important points about the problems experienced by the participants. Documents were also used to obtain data and information, such as the lecturer's notebooks and other documents related to the application of an assessment rubric based on Bloom's taxonomy. The collected data was later used to answer the research questions.

The first stage of data collection involved collating various information related to the two research questions. This information was obtained through initial observations, a literature

review, and consultations with experts in the field of educational psychology, so that the phenomena, concepts, and research themes could be made truly clear. The second stage was to approach the participants, so that they, as well as the department and university concerned, could accept the research. The third stage was to build good relationships with the participants and become familiar with their environment. This included learning about classroom learning activities, the way of thinking, the language used, and efforts to support ongoing research. The next stage was to test the research instrument on students who were not study participants but were in the same department, so we could establish if the applied instruments were sufficiently understood and communicative. After the instrument was found to be suitable, the author collected the required data for the analysis process. Finally, the researcher organized the various data that had been collected.

2.5. Data Analysis

Data analysis in qualitative research with a case study design is carried out systematically. Data were presented through the following stages: (1) The researcher created and organized files for the data. (2) The researcher read all the collected data, made marginal notes, and formed an initial code. (3) The researcher described the problem that was occurring and its context. (4) The researcher applied categorical aggregation to form themes and patterns. (5) The researcher performed a direct interpretation and then developed a naturalistic generalization about the lessons that could be learned. Finally, (6) the researcher presented an in-depth picture using a narrative to draw conclusions and suggest further research.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Applying Bloom's Taxonomy in a Rubric to Assess the Writing and Speaking of English

The first findings related to applying Bloom's taxonomy to assess students majoring in English at UIN RM Said. The cognitive element of the assessment results reflects the students' level of knowledge and understanding. The knowledge aspect focused on students' ability to use grammar and vocabulary, speak fluently, and use language that is suitable for the topic of the paper. The understanding aspect, meanwhile, focused on students' ability to understand instructions or problems, such as to use correct pronunciation, intonation, and word stress or repeat something in their own words using certain strategies. Thus, two levels were observed from Bloom's taxonomy. Meanwhile, outside the application level were the implementation, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation levels.

Analytical rubrics are used by teachers to guide assessment guidelines, and they have levels of assessment criteria that are described and assigned to an assessment scale. A created rubric must be trialed to ensure that it provides objective and consistent assessments. In this study, various findings supported these previous studies. The analytical rubric based on Bloom's taxonomy was used to handle assignments with many components, with it providing grades that reflected the students' strengths and weaknesses when writing and speaking English.

The assessment of paper-writing ability was based on students' knowledge of writing words and using clear sentence structures. In this stage, students are introduced to writing as a complete skill and tested on it. Writing is generally the language skill that is mastered last by language learners. This is because compared to speaking skills, writing skills are more difficult for non-native language speakers to acquire, especially at an elementary level. This inevitably challenges teachers regarding improving their students' writing ability in a foreign language. It should also be understood that foreign language speaking skills are similar to composing

skills, and these two productive skills are integrated. By the word “productive” here, we mean that when people speak, they use language to produce a conversation. In contrast, “integrated” means that speaking arises from several abilities that play a role in speaking skills.

The assessment guidelines refer to the guidelines for preparing higher education curricula. There are four components in the rubric for English writing and speaking: a description of the paper assignment, a mastery level scale, the sort of level that students must achieve, and a description of the language mastery. These are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.
Analytical Rubric for Assessing English Writing and Speaking

Appraised dimensions	Scale				
	Very Poor (Score < 20)	Poor (21-40)	Sufficient (41-60)	Good (61-80)	Very Good (Score ≥ 81)
Writing	The paper is irregularly written and does not reflect adequate grammar, vocabulary, understanding, or language suitability.	The paper is quite focused but lacking in terms of grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, and appropriate language.	The paper reflects good grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, and appropriate language.	The paper is well organized and supported by good grammar, vocabulary, comprehension, and appropriate language.	The paper presents knowledge and understanding that is in accordance with the topic, and this is supported by good use of grammar, vocabulary, understanding, and suitable language.
Speaking	Students are anxious and uncomfortable and need to read various notes. They lack accuracy in pronunciation, intonation, word stress, and strategy.	Students focus on papers with monotonous intonation.	Students speak fluently but their pronunciation accuracy, intonation, word stress, and strategies are lacking.	Students speak fluently and have accurate pronunciation, clear intonation, and sufficient word stress, but they lack sufficient strategy.	Students speak fluently and enthusiastically with good pronunciation, intonation, word stress, and strategy.

Table 1 describes the assessment rubric format used by lecturers for English writing and speaking. Language appropriateness relates to the extent to which English is used in accordance with the communication context and the topic at hand, while strategy relates to students' efforts to overcome problems that arise during class presentations and discussions. Through this rubric, students' achievements can be measured, and they get fast feedback.

Various steps were taken in the application of this rubric: The first step was to prepare the students by introducing them to Bloom's taxonomy. After presenting these levels and some examples to the students, the lecturer asked them to put this information into practice. A good way to do this is by asking students to write papers about interesting topics that have been explained by the lecturer. Students were required to interpret the background of a

problem topic and then restate it in their own words. They then presented it in a group discussion in English. Students also wrote papers based on videos they were shown in class. The lecturers also asked students to provide examples of recommended suggestions as a way to guide them to the sort of answer that the lecturer was looking for.

After presenting the information and putting it into practice, the lecturer then invited the students to practice using the material they had been taught in class. The class together could compose a paper with appropriate writing and foreign-language speaking skills, so they could see what would be expected of them when they were to complete Bloom's Taxonomy assessment on their own. In its application, the taxonomy group had the lowest and highest levels, which referred to the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy. The evaluation involved the frequency (f) and percentage (%). Table 1 shows the frequency of students' cognitive levels when assessing paper assignments with the rubric.

Table 2.
Frequency and Percentage of English Writing Skills

	Rubric level	f	%
Low	Student knowledge	78	73
	Student perceptions	18	27
	Application	0	0
High	Analysis	0	0
	Synthesis	0	0
	Evaluation	0	0
Total		96	100
Chi-Square (Asymp. Significant)		0.000	0.000

Table 1 shows that the assessment rubric includes the level of knowledge and understanding in a reflection of Bloom's taxonomy. This means that foreign-language writing is based on the lowest level of cognition in Bloom's taxonomy, namely knowledge. The vocabulary of a paper does include a high level of cognition, however. The percentage score for the knowledge level in student papers is 73% compared with 27% for understanding. Table 1 therefore clearly shows that there is a large gap between the levels of knowledge and perception. Presented below is the scheme for a paper that was to be written by students and presented in class.

- Chapter 1 (Introduction)
 - ⇒ Background to the paper, which contains the background to the problem being considered by the student
 - ⇒ Problem formulation, which specifies the problem in the form of questions that will be answered and explained in the paper
 - ⇒ Purpose of the paper
- Chapter II (Discussion)
- Chapter III (Conclusion)
 - ⇒ Conclusions drawn from the discussion in the previous chapter
 - ⇒ Suggestions for readers who may want to address the same problem
- Bibliography

When assessing students' written papers, lecturers use this scheme, which is communicated to students from the start. Several brief explanations were provided by the lecturers such as for (1) starting with a global paragraph supported by clear data sources, (2) logically organizing the text, and (3) using good diction and grammar.

Table 2 shows the frequency of cognitive levels used by students for the speaking assessment rubric, which was based on paper presentations and class discussions.

Table 3.
Frequencies and Percentages for Speaking English

	Rubric level	f	%
Low	Student knowledge	91	70
	Perception	27	30
	Application	0	0
High	Analysis	0	0
	Synthesis	0	0
	Evaluation rubric assessment	0	0
Total		118	100
Chi-Square (Asymp. Significant)		0.000	0.000

Table 2 shows that the assessment rubric again includes the levels of knowledge and understanding, so speaking a foreign language involves cognitive levels from Bloom's taxonomy. Nevertheless, the researcher detected no level of application, analysis, synthesis, or evaluation. The knowledge level when presenting papers was scored at 70%, while the level of understanding was scored at 30%.

The second step in this assessment is to clarify what the students should learn from the lessons being taught and then choose one of the topics before asking several questions based on each level. Students must answer various questions, with one corresponding to each level of Bloom's taxonomy. This cycle of knowledge indicates a deeper understanding on the part of the learner.

When assessing students, better paper writing and English speaking skills should be awarded additional points, and to assess this fairly, the lecturer establishes an effective rubric. Rubrics allow students to earn partial points depending on how complete and accurate their writing and speaking skills are. One of the best ways for lecturers to make learning more interesting is to give students several choices, especially at higher levels, so they generally give students two or three choices at each level, thus enabling them to choose topics they are most confident about completing correctly.

When learning writing, the application of Bloom's taxonomy focuses on students' cognitive skills, namely by developing higher-order thinking skills (HOTS). The learning process involves playing videos in class and discussing certain currently relevant phenomena. The learning videos are intended to introduce students to words related to certain topics, so students can easily recognize them in the video and remember the vocabulary. The lecturer then sets an assignment to write a scientific paper based on the topic portrayed in the video. Their understanding is later determined by assessing the assignment. The students use the gained vocabulary to write papers and discuss them in front of the class, with the class reviewing and discussing the pros and cons of the various papers. Following this, students then discuss the solutions being offered to resolve the phenomenon being studied. Based on previous assignments, students can write proposals for improvement.

Although there are assessment rubrics available for paper assignments, lecturers also use written exams as a tool for assessing students' learning outcomes. Systematic writing and language assessment plays an important role in testing students' overall cognitive level. Previous studies have revealed that Bloom's taxonomy is useful as a framework for creating learning objectives, and language-learning goals are important because they provide a road

map for students. By keeping the learning objectives in mind, students can direct their efforts more appropriately and monitor their learning progress over the course.

Other studies have found that clear and logical English-language learning objectives at the module level help students to make connections between training outcomes, learning activities, and assessments (Northern Illinois University, 2020). Moreover, well-written learning objectives must use SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely) elements. The verbs used must also represent a level of performance expectation that is measurable and observable, such as by using the action verbs provided at each level of Bloom's taxonomy. The semester learning plan (RPS) shows the learning objectives set by the teaching lecturer. For example, the learning objective for an English literature course states, "In this RPS, students will become able to write, analyze, and understand various traditional and contemporary literary genres, including linguistic and literary aspects in English literary works."

Based on the first set of results, we can conclude that the application of an assessment rubric for English-language writing and speaking makes students more likely to apply knowledge rather than memorize information. They also seek to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In class discussions, students engage in activities that are rather compelling, interesting, and collaborative, so most of them become more confident in using English and are satisfied and active in the learning process.

Although the application of the assessment rubric for English writing and speaking is rather good, it has drawbacks in terms of authentic assessment, which tends to be difficult because grammar that is learned within a context cannot be tested out of context. Generally, the way to do this is to use a computer with several software programs installed, and students can submit their assignments over the internet. The goal is to obtain feedback or send their output electronically to experts for evaluation. Comments from these external evaluators can then be counted toward the grades for assignments completed by students. Computers can also be used to create rubrics and record observations and reflections. They can also help lecturers and students to keep track of the total points earned. They can also serve as a tool during assessment to help teachers record, summarize, and report the progress of their students' learning outcomes.

3.2. Benefits of the Rubric for Assessing Writing and Speaking for English Language Education Students

The second goal of this study was to reveal the benefits of applying a rubric to assess English writing and speaking. The main benefit was found to be students having greater motivation when completing paper-writing assignments and presenting them before the class. Student motivation reflects in the students' efforts to fulfill the criteria of the assessment rubric, which is based on Bloom's taxonomy. A study investigating English students found that they are more intrinsically motivated to prepare for a future profession when compared to students with other majors (Ngo *et al.*, 2017). Our findings provide new evidence to support the notion that applying Bloom's taxonomy can further reinforce the motivation to learn English. The application of Bloom's taxonomy in assessment rubrics also helps lecturers to obtain standardized measures of students' learning achievements when writing scientific papers and speaking in English. Furthermore, Bloom's taxonomy can test the relevance of the goals and objectives in the RPS.

Benefits were also revealed through the interviews with teaching lecturers. They expressed that the first benefit they felt when applying Bloom's taxonomy was its ability to increase the objectivity and consistency of the assessment of various courses in the English department, such as for grammar, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics. Previous literature has explained that rubrics provide an effective standard for increasing the objectivity of assessment, so they can help limit any bias and consistently assess students' levels of cognitive complexity and ensure they make significant improvements (Reddy & Andrade, 2010). Learning English can enhance self-confidence and problem-solving skills, which are measures of a person's professionalism, as well as improve the ability to adapt to people from various backgrounds (Galloway & Ruegg, 2020). Thus, the first benefit of using a rubric is the support for learning the English language in various courses.

The second benefit is that it helps students to understand the standards expected in the assignments set by the lecturer, as well as the assessment criteria. Nevertheless, applying Bloom's taxonomy to rubrics can have advantages and disadvantages (Andrade *et al.*, 2019). For example, some students had difficulty explaining the keywords they found in the rubric. In reality, students tend to see rubrics as a teaching tool, while teachers are more likely to see them as a time-saving tool for learning assessment (Li & Lindsey, 2015). This second benefit will therefore vary in its degree for each individual student, because some students may experience greater difficulty in understanding the criteria set by the lecturer.

A third benefit lies in analytical rubrics facilitating the provision of fairly specific and targeted feedback to students. According to Jonsson and Svingby (2007), facilitating effective feedback can help students make improvements and increase the quality of their work. Various studies have criticized assessment rubrics, however, especially when applied formatively when detailed information about student performance is needed. A fourth benefit relates to increasing students' involvement in the learning process. For example, the use of rubrics for self-assessment and the assessment of others can enhance the role of students in the learning process, help to develop metacognitive and self-thinking abilities, and improve the quality of their learning (Panadero & Jonsson, 2013). Learning English also helps students to develop a broader understanding of cultural diversity and improves general learning abilities (Benmokhtari, 2021). Based on this explanation, this fourth benefit provides new evidence to support the positive impact of applying Bloom's taxonomy in assessment rubrics for English assignments.

A fifth benefit is the increased efficiency in assessment when using clear and specific standards. Previous studies have cited the benefits of using Bloom's taxonomy and assessment rubrics to reduce the time needed to provide feedback when teaching (Andrade, 2000). In practice, lecturers check their students' level of knowledge and understanding of writing and speaking English based on topics they have discussed in class. The results of the interviews can be summarized in the quote below:

Lecturers explained that they incorporate Bloom's taxonomy into teaching in many ways, such as making students remember active vocabulary when writing and speaking, applying grammar rules, and analyzing them. When teaching, certain points are briefly explained, and then the lecturer will ask students what they understand. Students will also be given the task of writing a scientific paper and presenting it to help them understand what they are learning.

By classifying different levels of cognitive ability, using Bloom's taxonomy within teaching English writing and speaking helps lecturers to set clear goals for the class, find appropriate approaches for different types of lessons, and choose the best way to measure learning

progress in the English language. Through this model, lecturers also encourage their students to continue to progress and give their best. In addition to such theoretical applications, new rubrics and scales can be digitalized (or digital rubrics can be developed) to provide users with assessment tools that check on learners' development of speaking and writing skills (Atabek, 2020).

4. Conclusion

The lecturers understood that the rubric for assessing English-language writing and speaking based on Bloom's taxonomy can help assess aspects of student learning, especially cognitive aspects at certain levels. In practice, this increases students' motivation to perform satisfactorily. It can, therefore, be concluded that applying Bloom's taxonomy in an assessment rubric provides extraordinary benefits for students and lecturers.

This research contributes to the literature by demonstrating that assessment rubrics for foreign-language writing and speaking can be improved with Bloom's taxonomy and its six levels. Indeed, this research shows that integrating Bloom's Taxonomy into assessment rubrics has the potential to improve assessment quality and consistently evaluate student performance. The recommendations offered here, therefore, focus on efforts to optimize the use of Bloom's taxonomy when trying to create a more accurate and comprehensive rubric.

This research revealed that using Bloom's taxonomy in assessment rubrics requires teachers to understand each domain and subdomain well. Thus, consistent training should be provided to rubric users, such as lecturers and supervisors, to ensure they have an accurate understanding and can apply the taxonomy correctly. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the use of rubrics and Bloom's taxonomy are also crucial because it is essential to identify and address any problems that arise from the use of rubrics, thereby supporting improved learning outcomes. The findings also indicate that developing a complete and detailed rubric is an essential step in using Bloom's taxonomy, so it is necessary to review and update the rubric periodically to ensure student performance can be assessed thoroughly and accurately.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors declared that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 11/08/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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